

**ANALYTIC CONTINUATION OF APOSTOL-VU MULTIPLE
BALANCING ZETA FUNCTIONS**

Prasanta Kumar Ray

Department of Mathematics, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar, Burla, India
prasantamath@suniv.ac.in

Utkal Keshari Dutta

Department of Mathematics, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar, Burla, India
utkaldutta@gmail.com

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Abstract

In this note we introduce Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta functions as

$$\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_r; s_{r+1}) = \sum_{1 \leq m_1 < \dots < m_r < \infty} \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1} B_{m_2}^{s_2} \cdots B_{m_r}^{s_r} B_{m_1+m_2+\dots+m_r}^{s_{r+1}}},$$

where s_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r+1$) are complex variables. We study the analytic continuation of Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta functions of three variables and calculate a complete list of the residues corresponding to their respective poles. Further we examine the values of these zeta functions at negative integers.

1. Introduction

The Euler-Zagier multiple zeta function of depth r is defined by

$$\zeta(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_r) = \sum_{1 \leq m_1 < m_2 < \dots < m_r < \infty} \frac{1}{m_1^{s_1} m_2^{s_2} \cdots m_r^{s_r}},$$

where s_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r$) are complex variables [13]. Zhao [14] gave an analytic continuation of $\zeta(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_r)$ as a function of s_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r$) to \mathbb{C}^r using Gelfand and Shilov's generalized functions. The series

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n < m} \frac{1}{m^{s_1} n^{s_2} (m+n)} \tag{1.1}$$

was first introduced by Apostol and Vu [2] and they obtained partial results on its analytic continuation. The meromorphic continuation of (1.1), and the more

general series

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n < m} \frac{1}{m^{s_1} n^{s_2} (m+n)^{s_3}} \tag{1.2}$$

to the whole space, was first proved in [6]. In [7], Matsumoto generalized (1.2) and introduced the Apostol-Vu r -ple zeta function

$$\begin{aligned} & \zeta_{AV,r}(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_r; s_{r+1}) \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq m_1 < m_2 < \dots < m_r < \infty} \frac{1}{m_1^{s_1} m_2^{s_2} \dots m_r^{s_r} (m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_r)^{s_{r+1}}}. \end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

He proved that the series (1.3) is convergent absolutely when $\text{Re}(s_i) > 1$ ($1 \leq i \leq r$), $\text{Re}(s_{r+1}) > 0$, and can be extended meromorphically to the whole space \mathbb{C}^{r+1} .

Let $\{F_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be the sequence of Fibonacci numbers which is recursively defined by

$$F_0 = 0, F_1 = 1, F_{n+1} = F_n + F_{n-1}, \text{ for } n \geq 1.$$

The closed form expression for $\{F_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ is $F_n = \frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\alpha - \beta}$, where $\alpha = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ and $\beta = \frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2}$ are the zeros of the Fibonacci characteristic equation $x^2 - x - 1 = 0$. Navas [8] introduced the Fibonacci zeta function $\zeta_F(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} F_n^{-s}$, where F_n denotes the n -th Fibonacci number, and proved that $\zeta_F(s)$ is meromorphically continued to the whole complex plane \mathbb{C} . For $s = 1$, $\zeta_F(1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} F_n^{-1}$ is the sum of the reciprocal of Fibonacci constants which is an irrational number [1]. Duverney et al. [4] proved that $\zeta_F(2m)$ for $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ are all transcendental numbers. Elsner et al. [5] proved that $\zeta_F(2)$, $\zeta_F(4)$ and $\zeta_F(6)$ are algebraically independent. By applying the theory of modular forms, Ram Murty [9] also showed that $\zeta_F(2m)$ are transcendental numbers for $m \geq 1$. Recently, Rout and Meher [11] defined the multiple Fibonacci zeta function of depth r as:

$$\zeta_F(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_r) = \sum_{1 \leq m_1 < m_2 < \dots < m_r < \infty} \frac{1}{F_{m_1}^{s_1} F_{m_2}^{s_2} \dots F_{m_r}^{s_r}}.$$

They studied the analytic continuation of $\zeta_F(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_r)$ of depth 2, and found a complete list of poles and their corresponding residues. In [11], they also examined the arithmetic nature of multiple Fibonacci zeta functions at negative integer arguments.

Before going to the study of analytic continuation of Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta functions, our foremost task is to discuss the theory of balancing numbers and balancing zeta function. A natural number m is said to be a balancing number if it is the solution of a simple Diophantine equation $1 + 2 + \dots + (m - 1) = (m + 1) + (m + 2) + \dots + (m + r)$, where r is a balancer corresponding to m [3]. Let $\{B_m\}_{m \geq 0}$ be the balancing sequence which is recursively defined as $B_0 = 0$, $B_1 = 1$ and $B_m = 6B_{m-1} - B_{m-2}$ for $m \geq 2$. The closed form expression for

$\{B_m\}_{m \geq 0}$ is $B_m = \frac{\alpha^m - \beta^m}{\alpha - \beta}$, where $\alpha = 3 + 2\sqrt{2}$ and $\beta = \alpha^{-1} = 3 - 2\sqrt{2}$ are the roots of the balancing characteristic equation $x^2 - 6x + 1 = 0$ [10]. Rout and Panda [12] considered balancing zeta function $\zeta_B(s) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} B_m^{-s}$, $\text{Re}(s) > 0$ for $s \in \mathbb{C}$, where B_m denotes the m -th balancing number, and derived that $\zeta_B(s)$ can be meromorphically continued to the whole complex plane.

In the present study we introduce the Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta function and investigate its analytic continuation of three variable along with poles and their corresponding residues. We also evaluate the values of Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta functions at negative integers.

2. Analytic Continuation of Apostol-Vu Multiple Balancing Zeta Functions

In this section we define the Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta function and study its analytic continuation of three variables. *The Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta function* is defined by

$$\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_r; s_{r+1}) = \sum_{1 \leq m_1 < \dots < m_r < \infty} \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1} B_{m_2}^{s_2} \cdots B_{m_r}^{s_r} B_{m_1+m_2+\dots+m_r}^{s_{r+1}}}, \tag{2.1}$$

where s_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r + 1$) are complex variables.

Proposition 1. *The series $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3) = \sum_{1 \leq m_1 < m_2 < \infty} \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1} B_{m_2}^{s_2} B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_3}}$ converges absolutely in the domain*

$$D_3 = \{(s_1, s_2, s_3) \in \mathbb{C}^3 | \text{Re}(s_i) > 0, i = 1, 2, 3\}.$$

Proof. Let $s_j = \sigma_j + iy_j \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\sigma_j = \text{Re}(s_j) > 0$, $j = 1, 2, 3$. From (2.1), we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3) &= \sum_{1 \leq m_1 < m_2 < \infty} \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1} B_{m_2}^{s_2} B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_3}} \\ &= \sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1}} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_2} B_{2m_1+m_2}^{s_3}}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1}} \right| &= (\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_1} \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha^{m_1} - \beta^{m_1})^{s_1}} \right| \\ &\leq (\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_1} \frac{1}{\alpha^{m_1 \sigma_1} (1 - (\frac{\beta}{\alpha})^{m_1})^{\sigma_1}} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{\alpha - \beta}{1 - |\beta/\alpha|} \right)^{\sigma_1} \frac{1}{\alpha^{\sigma_1 m_1}} \\ &= \Lambda_{\sigma_1} \frac{(\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_1}}{\alpha^{\sigma_1 m_1}}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

where $\Lambda_{\sigma_1} = \frac{1}{(1 - |\beta/\alpha|)^{\sigma_1}}$. Similarly,

$$\left| \frac{1}{B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_2}} \right| \leq \Lambda_{\sigma_2} \frac{(\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_2}}{\alpha^{\sigma_2(m_1+m_2)}} \tag{2.4}$$

and

$$\left| \frac{1}{B_{2m_1+m_2}^{s_3}} \right| \leq \Lambda_{\sigma_3} \frac{(\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_3}}{\alpha^{\sigma_3(2m_1+m_2)}}, \tag{2.5}$$

where $\Lambda_{\sigma_j} = \frac{1}{(1 - |\beta/\alpha|)^{\sigma_j}}$ for $j = 2, 3$. By virtue of (2.2), (2.3), (2.4) and (2.5),

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1} B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_2} B_{2m_1+m_2}^{s_3}} \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1}} \right| \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{1}{B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_2} B_{2m_1+m_2}^{s_3}} \right| \\ &\leq \Lambda_{\sigma_1} \Lambda_{\sigma_2} \Lambda_{\sigma_3} (\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3} \sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\alpha^{\sigma_1 m_1}} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\alpha^{\sigma_2(m_1+m_2)} \times \alpha^{\sigma_3(2m_1+m_2)}} \\ &= \Lambda (\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3} \sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\alpha^{(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + 2\sigma_3)m_1}} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\alpha^{(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)m_2}} \\ &= \Lambda (\alpha - \beta)^{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + 2\sigma_3} - 1)} \times \frac{1}{(\alpha^{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3} - 1)} \\ &< \infty, \end{aligned}$$

as $\alpha > 1$ where $\Lambda = \Lambda_{\sigma_1} \Lambda_{\sigma_2} \Lambda_{\sigma_3}$. Therefore, the series (2.2) converges absolutely in the domain D_3 , which ends the proof. \square

Theorem 1. *The series $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ can be analytically continued to a meromorphic function on \mathbb{C}^3 . It has possible simple poles on the hyperplanes*

$$s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 = -2(k + l + 2t) + \frac{2\pi ia}{\log \alpha} \text{ with } k, l, t \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, a \in \mathbb{Z},$$

and

$$s_2 + s_3 = -2(l + t) + \frac{2\pi ib}{\log \alpha} \text{ with } l, t \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, b \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Proof. For any $s = \sigma + iy \in \mathbb{C}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} B_m^s &= \left(\frac{\alpha^m - \beta^m}{4\sqrt{2}}\right)^s = (4\sqrt{2})^{-s} \alpha^{ms} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right)^m\right)^s \\ &= 2^{-\frac{5s}{2}} \alpha^{ms} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^{2m}}\right)^s \\ &= 2^{-\frac{5s}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{s}{k} \alpha^{m(s-2k)}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

The above series converges since $\alpha > 1$. By virtue of (2.2) and (2.6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1} B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_2} B_{2m_1+m_2}^{s_3}} \\ &= \sum_{m_1, m_2=1}^{\infty} 2^{\frac{5s_1}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \alpha^{-m_1(s_1+2k)} \times 2^{\frac{5s_2}{2}} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \alpha^{-(m_1+m_2)(s_2+2l)} \\ &\quad \times 2^{\frac{5s_3}{2}} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \alpha^{-(2m_1+m_2)(s_3+2t)}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

We know that $\left|\binom{-s}{k}\right| \leq (-1)^k \binom{-|s|}{k}$. Thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{1}{B_{m_1}^{s_1} B_{m_1+m_2}^{s_2} B_{2m_1+m_2}^{s_3}} \right| \\ &= \sum_{m_1, m_2=1}^{\infty} \left| 2^{\frac{5s_1}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \alpha^{-m_1(s_1+2k)} \times 2^{\frac{5s_2}{2}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \alpha^{-(m_1+m_2)(s_2+2l)} 2^{\frac{5s_3}{2}} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \alpha^{-(2m_1+m_2)(s_3+2t)} \left. \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{m_1, m_2=1}^{\infty} 2^{\frac{5(\sigma_1+\sigma_2+\sigma_3)}{2}} \alpha^{-m_1\sigma_1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-|s_1|}{k} (-1)^k \alpha^{-2m_1k} \\ &\quad \times \alpha^{-(m_1+m_2)\sigma_2} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-|s_2|}{l} (-1)^l \alpha^{-2(m_1+m_2)l} \\ &\quad \times \alpha^{-(2m_1+m_2)\sigma_3} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-|s_3|}{t} (-1)^t \alpha^{-2(2m_1+m_2)t} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{m_1, m_2=1}^{\infty} 2^{\frac{5(\sigma_1+\sigma_2+\sigma_3)}{2}} \alpha^{-m_1\sigma_1} \left(1 - \alpha^{-2m_1}\right)^{-|s_1|} \times \alpha^{-(m_1+m_2)\sigma_2} \\
 &\quad \times \left(1 - \alpha^{-2(m_1+m_2)}\right)^{-|s_2|} \alpha^{-(2m_1+m_2)\sigma_3} \left(1 - \alpha^{-2(2m_1+m_2)}\right)^{-|s_3|} \\
 &\leq \sum_{m_1, m_2=1}^{\infty} 2^{\frac{5(\sigma_1+\sigma_2+\sigma_3)}{2}} \alpha^{-m_1\sigma_1} \left(1 - \alpha^{-2}\right)^{-|s_1|} \times \alpha^{-(m_1+m_2)\sigma_2} \left(1 - \alpha^{-4}\right)^{-|s_2|} \\
 &\quad \times \alpha^{-(2m_1+m_2)\sigma_3} \left(1 - \alpha^{-6}\right)^{-|s_3|} \\
 &= 2^{\frac{5(\sigma_1+\sigma_2+\sigma_3)}{2}} \left(1 - \alpha^{-2}\right)^{-|s_1|} \left(1 - \alpha^{-4}\right)^{-|s_2|} \left(1 - \alpha^{-6}\right)^{-|s_3|} \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \alpha^{-(\sigma_1+\sigma_2+2\sigma_3)m_1} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \alpha^{-(\sigma_2+\sigma_3)m_2} \\
 &< \infty.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the above series absolutely converges for a fixed point (s_1, s_2, s_3) in D_3 . Then by interchanging the order of summation in (2.7), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3) &= 2^{\frac{5(s_1+s_2+s_3)}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \\
 &\quad \sum_{m_1=1}^{\infty} \left(\alpha^{-(s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t)}\right)^{m_1} \sum_{m_2=1}^{\infty} \left(\alpha^{-(s_2+s_3+2l+2t)}\right)^{m_2} \\
 &= 2^{\frac{5(s_1+s_2+s_3)}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \\
 &\quad \frac{\alpha^{-(s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t)}}{\left(1 - \alpha^{-(s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t)}\right)} \times \frac{\alpha^{-(s_2+s_3+2l+2t)}}{\left(1 - \alpha^{-(s_2+s_3+2l+2t)}\right)} \\
 &= 2^{\frac{5(s_1+s_2+s_3)}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \\
 &\quad \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1\right)} \times \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1\right)}. \tag{2.8}
 \end{aligned}$$

For any $s_1, s_2, s_3 \in \mathbb{C}$, $|\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1| > \alpha^{\sigma_1+\sigma_2+2\sigma_3+k+l+2t}$ for $k \geq k_0$, $l \geq l_0$, $t \geq t_0$ and $|\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1| > \alpha^{\sigma_2+\sigma_3+l+t}$ for $l \geq l_1$, $t \geq t_1$, where $k_0 = k_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \alpha) \gg 0$, $l_0 = l_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \alpha) \gg 0$, $t_0 = t_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \alpha) \gg 0$, $l_1 = l_1(\sigma_2, \sigma_3, \alpha) \gg 0$, and $t_1 = t_1(\sigma_2, \sigma_3, \alpha) \gg 0$. Assume that $l^* = \max\{l_0, l_1\}$ and $t^* = \max\{t_0, t_1\}$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{k>k_0}^{\infty} \sum_{l>l^*}^{\infty} \sum_{t>t^*}^{\infty} \left| \binom{-s_1}{k} \binom{-s_2}{l} \binom{-s_3}{t} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1)} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \times \frac{1}{(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1)} \right| \\
 \leq & \sum_{\substack{k>k_0, \\ t>t^*}}^{\infty} \binom{-|s_1|}{k} (-1)^k \binom{-|s_2|}{l} (-1)^l \binom{-|s_3|}{t} (-1)^t \frac{1}{\alpha^{\sigma_1+\sigma_2+2\sigma_3+k+l+2t}} \\
 & \times \frac{1}{\alpha^{\sigma_2+\sigma_3+l+t}} \\
 \leq & \alpha^{-(\sigma_1+2\sigma_2+3\sigma_3)} \sum_{\substack{k>k_0, \\ t>t^*}}^{\infty} \binom{-|s_1|}{k} (-1)^k \alpha^{-k} \binom{-|s_2|}{l} (-1)^l \alpha^{-2l} \\
 & \times \binom{-|s_3|}{t} (-1)^t \alpha^{-3t} \\
 \leq & \alpha^{-(\sigma_1+2\sigma_2+3\sigma_3)} (1 - \alpha^{-1})^{-|s_1|} (1 - \alpha^{-2})^{-|s_2|} (1 - \alpha^{-3})^{-|s_3|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The above bound is uniform where (s_1, s_2, s_3) varies over compact subsets of \mathbb{C}^3 . Thus the series (2.8) converges uniformly and absolutely on the compact subsets of \mathbb{C}^3 not containing any poles. Indeed, the series (2.8) determines the holomorphic function on \mathbb{C}^3 except for the poles derived from the functions $\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1 = 0$ and $\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1 = 0$. Therefore, $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ can be analytically continued to a meromorphic function on \mathbb{C}^3 and its simple poles are at

$$s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 = -2(k + l + 2t) + \frac{2\pi ia}{\log \alpha} \text{ with } k, l, t \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, a \in \mathbb{Z}, \tag{2.9}$$

and

$$s_2 + s_3 = -2(l + t) + \frac{2\pi ib}{\log \alpha} \text{ with } l, t \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, b \in \mathbb{Z}. \tag{2.10}$$

This completes the proof. □

3. Residues of Apostol-Vu Multiple Balancing Zeta Functions at Poles

In this section, we find the residues of $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ at the simple poles derived from Theorem 1. We define the residue of the Apostol-Vu multiple balancing zeta

functions $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ along the hyperplane (2.9) to be the restriction of the meromorphic function

$$\left(s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 + 2(k + l + 2t) - \frac{2\pi ia}{\log \alpha}\right) \zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$$

to the hyperplane (2.9). Similarly, define the residue of $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ along the hyperplane (2.10) to be the restriction of the meromorphic function

$$\left(s_2 + s_3 + 2(l + t) - \frac{2\pi ib}{\log \alpha}\right) \zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$$

to the hyperplane (2.10).

Theorem 2. *The residue of $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ at $s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 = s_{k',l',t'} = -2(k' + l' + 2t') + \frac{2\pi ia}{\log \alpha}$ with $k', l', t' \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ is*

$$\frac{2^{\frac{5s_{k',l',t'}}{2}}}{\log \alpha} \sum_{\substack{t, l, k \geq 0 \\ k+l+2t=k'+l'+2t'}} 2^{-\frac{5s_3}{2}} \binom{-s_3}{t} \binom{-s_2}{l} \binom{-s_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1)}.$$

Proof. Let $k', l', t' \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and $a \in \mathbb{Z}$. The function $\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k'+2l'+4t'} - 1$ is an analytic function which has simple zeros at

$$s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 = s_{k',l',t'} = -2(k' + l' + 2t') + \frac{2\pi ia}{\log \alpha}.$$

Now, $\lim_{\substack{s_1+s_2+2s_3 \\ \rightarrow s_{k',l',t'}}} \frac{s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 - s_{k',l',t'}}{\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k'+2l'+4t'} - 1} = \frac{1}{\log \alpha}$. The residue of $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ along $s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 = s_{k',l',t'}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Res}_{\substack{s_1+s_2+2s_3 \\ \rightarrow s_{k',l',t'}}} \zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3) \\ &= \lim_{\substack{s_1+s_2+2s_3 \\ \rightarrow s_{k',l',t'}}} \left(s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 - s_{k',l',t'}\right) 2^{\frac{5(s_1+s_2+s_3)}{2}} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \\ & \quad \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1)} \\ & \quad \times \frac{1}{(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2^{-\frac{5s_3}{2}} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1\right)} \Big|_{s_1+s_2+2s_3=s_{k',l',t'}} \\
 &\quad \times \lim_{\substack{s_1+s_2+2s_3 \\ \rightarrow s_{k',l',t'}}} 2^{\frac{5(s_1+s_2+2s_3)}{2}} \frac{s_1+s_2+2s_3-s_{k',l',t'}}{\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t}-1} \\
 &= \frac{2^{\frac{5s_{k',l',t'}}{2}}}{\log \alpha} \sum_{\substack{t,l,k \geq 0 \\ k+l+2t=k'+l'+2t'}} 2^{-\frac{5s_3}{2}} \binom{-s_3}{t} \binom{-s_2}{l} \binom{-s_1}{k} \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1\right)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This finishes the proof. □

Theorem 3. Let $l', t' \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and $b \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then the residue of $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ at $s_2 + s_3 = s_{l',t'} = -2(l' + t') + \frac{2\pi ib}{\log \alpha}$ is

$$\frac{2^{\frac{5s_{l',t'}}{2}}}{\log \alpha} \sum_{\substack{t,l,k \geq 0 \\ l+t=l'+t'}} 2^{\frac{5s_1}{2}} \binom{-s_3}{t} \binom{-s_2}{l} \binom{-s_1}{k} \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1\right)}.$$

Proof. The function $\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l'+2t'} - 1$ is an analytic function which has simple zeros at

$$s_2 + s_3 = s_{l',t'} = -2(l' + t') + \frac{2\pi ib}{\log \alpha} \text{ with } l', t' \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \text{ and } b \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Now,

$$\lim_{s_2+s_3 \rightarrow s_{l',t'}} \frac{s_2 + s_3 - s_{l',t'}}{\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l'+2t'} - 1} = \operatorname{Res}_{s_2+s_3 = s_{l',t'}} \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l'+2t'} - 1\right)} = \frac{1}{\log \alpha}.$$

The residue of $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ along $s_2 + s_3 = s_{l',t'}$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\operatorname{Res}_{\substack{s_2+s_3 \\ \rightarrow s_{l',t'}}} \zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3) \\
 &= \lim_{\substack{s_2+s_3 \\ \rightarrow s_{l',t'}}} \left(s_2 + s_3 - s_{l',t'}\right) 2^{\frac{5(s_1+s_2+s_3)}{2}} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \\
 &\quad \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1\right)} \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1\right)} \\
 &= 2^{\frac{5s_1}{2}} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_3}{t} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_2}{l} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s_1}{k} \frac{1}{\left(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1\right)} \Big|_{s_2+s_3=s_{l',t'}} \\
 &\quad \times \lim_{\substack{s_2+s_3 \\ \rightarrow s_{l',t'}}} 2^{\frac{5(s_2+s_3)}{2}} \frac{s_2 + s_3 - s_{l',t'}}{\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{2^{\frac{5s_{l',t'}}{2}}}{\log \alpha} \sum_{\substack{t,l,k \geq 0 \\ l+t=l'+t'}} 2^{\frac{5s_1}{2}} \binom{-s_3}{t} \binom{-s_2}{l} \binom{-s_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1)}.$$

This ends the proof. □

4. Values of Apostol-Vu Multiple Balancing Zeta Functions at Negative Integers

In this section we consider the values of $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ at negative integers. First we give a sufficient condition for $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ to be holomorphic at $(s_1, s_2, s_3) = (-r_1, -r_2, -r_3)$ where $r_i \in \mathbb{N}$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Lemma 1. *Let $(r_1, r_2, r_3) \in \mathbb{N}^3$. Then $\zeta_{AVB}(s_1, s_2, s_3)$ is holomorphic at $(s_1, s_2, s_3) = (-r_1, -r_2, -r_3)$ if and only if $r_1 + r_2 + 2r_3 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, $r_2 + r_3 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2}$.*

Proof. The infinite series (2.8) is holomorphic except the poles derived from

$$(\alpha^{s_1+s_2+2s_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1) \times (\alpha^{s_2+s_3+2l+2t} - 1) = 0$$

This is true if and only if, one of the following equations holds:

$$s_1 + s_2 + 2s_3 = -2(k + l + 2t), s_2 + s_3 = -2(l + t),$$

for $(k, l, t) \in \mathbb{N}^3$, and the result follows. □

Theorem 4. *For positive integers $r_i, i = 1, 2, 3$, $\zeta_{AVB}(-r_1, -r_2, -r_3) \in \mathbb{Q}$ if even number of r_i in (r_1, r_2, r_3) are odd and $\zeta_{AVB}(-r_1, -r_2, -r_3) \in \sqrt{2}\mathbb{Q}$ if odd number of r_i in (r_1, r_2, r_3) are odd except for singularities.*

Proof. For positive integers r_1, r_2, r_3 , from (2.8) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{AVB}(-r_1, -r_2, -r_3) &= 2^{\frac{-5(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{r_1}{k} \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \binom{r_2}{l} \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \binom{r_3}{t} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_1-r_2-2r_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1)} \times \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_2-r_3+2l+2t} - 1)}. \end{aligned}$$

For $k > r_1, l > r_2$ and $t > r_3$, $\binom{r_1}{k}, \binom{r_2}{l}$ and $\binom{r_3}{t}$ vanish respectively. Thus this is a finite sum belonging to $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{AVB}(-r_1, -r_2, -r_3) &= 2^{\frac{-5(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \binom{r_1}{k} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \binom{r_2}{l} \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \binom{r_3}{t} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_1-r_2-2r_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1)} \times \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_2-r_3+2l+2t} - 1)}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

Let

$$\sigma_{l,t} = \binom{r_2}{l} \binom{r_3}{t} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_2-r_3+2l+2t} - 1)} \text{ and } \theta_{k,l,t} = \binom{r_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_1-r_2-2r_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1)}.$$

Using these identities, from (4.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \zeta_{AVB}(-r_1, -r_2, -r_3) \\ &= 5^{\frac{-(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}} \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,t} \theta_{k,l,t} \\ &= \frac{2^{\frac{-5(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}}}{2} \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,t} \theta_{k,l,t} + \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,r_3-t} \theta_{k,l,r_3-t} \right] \\ &= \frac{2^{\frac{-5(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}}}{4} \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,t} \theta_{k,l,t} + \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,t} \theta_{k,r_2-l,t} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,r_3-t} \theta_{k,l,r_3-t} + \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,r_3-t} \theta_{k,r_2-l,r_3-t} \right) \right] \\ &= \frac{2^{\frac{-5(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}}}{8} \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \left(\left(\sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,t} \theta_{k,l,t} + \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,t} \theta_{r_1-k,l,t} \right) + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,t} \theta_{k,r_2-l,t} \right. \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,t} \theta_{r_1-k,r_2-l,t} \right) + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,r_3-t} \theta_{k,l,r_3-t} + \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,r_3-t} \theta_{r_1-k,l,r_3-t} \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,r_3-t} \theta_{k,r_2-l,r_3-t} + \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,r_3-t} \theta_{r_1-k,r_2-l,r_3-t} \right) \right]. \tag{4.2} \end{aligned}$$

Let us denote:

$$\begin{aligned} P &= \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,t} \theta_{k,l,t}, \quad Q = \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,t} \theta_{r_1-k,l,t}, \quad R = \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,t} \theta_{k,r_2-l,t}, \\ S &= \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,t} \theta_{r_1-k,r_2-l,t}, \quad T = \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,r_3-t} \theta_{k,l,r_3-t}, \\ U &= \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{l,r_3-t} \theta_{r_1-k,l,r_3-t}, \quad V = \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,r_3-t} \theta_{k,r_2-l,r_3-t} \\ \text{and } W &= \sum_{t=0}^{r_3} \sum_{l=0}^{r_2} \sum_{k=0}^{r_1} \sigma_{r_2-l,r_3-t} \theta_{r_1-k,r_2-l,r_3-t}. \text{ Let } X = P+Q+R+S+T+U+V+W \end{aligned}$$

and $\Phi \neq \text{Id}$ be an automorphism of $\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2})/\mathbb{Q})$ and hence $\Phi(\alpha) = \beta$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma_{r_2-l, r_3-t} \theta_{r_1-k, r_2-l, r_3-t} \\ &= \binom{r_2}{r_2-l} \binom{r_3}{r_3-t} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_2-r_3+2(r_2-l)+2(r_3-t)} - 1)} \\ & \times \binom{r_1}{r_1-k} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{-r_1-r_2-2r_3+2(r_1-k)+2(r_2-l)+4(r_3-t)} - 1)} \\ &= \binom{r_3}{t} \binom{r_2}{l} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{r_2+r_3-2(l+t)} - 1)} \binom{r_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\alpha^{r_1+r_2+2r_3-2(k+l+2t)} - 1)} \\ &= \binom{r_3}{t} \binom{r_2}{l} \frac{1}{(\beta^{-r_2-r_3+2l+2t} - 1)} \binom{r_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\beta^{-r_1-r_2-2r_3+2k+2l+4t} - 1)}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

Similarly, one can deduce that

$$\sigma_{r_2-l, r_3-t} \theta_{k, r_2-l, r_3-t} = \binom{r_3}{t} \binom{r_2}{l} \frac{1}{(\beta^{-r_2-r_3+2(l+t)} - 1)} \binom{r_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\beta^{r_1-r_2-2r_3-2(k-l-2t)} - 1)}, \tag{4.4}$$

$$\sigma_{l, r_3-t} \theta_{r_1-k, l, r_3-t} = \binom{r_3}{t} \binom{r_2}{l} \frac{1}{(\beta^{r_2-r_3-2(l-t)} - 1)} \binom{r_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\beta^{-r_1+r_2-2r_3+2k-2l+4t} - 1)} \tag{4.5}$$

and

$$\sigma_{l, r_3-t} \theta_{k, l, r_3-t} = \binom{r_3}{t} \binom{r_2}{l} \frac{1}{(\beta^{r_2-r_3-2(l-t)} - 1)} \binom{r_1}{k} \frac{1}{(\beta^{r_1+r_2-2r_3-2(k+l-2t)} - 1)}. \tag{4.6}$$

Let \mathcal{N}_o and \mathcal{N}_e denote the set of odd and even positive integers respectively. We consider two cases.

Case 1. $r_1, r_2, r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_e$ (or) $r_1, r_2 \in \mathcal{N}_o$ and $r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_e$ (or) $r_1, r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_o$ and $r_2 \in \mathcal{N}_e$ (or) $r_2, r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_o$ and $r_1 \in \mathcal{N}_e$. In this case, $(r_1 + r_2 + r_3)/2$ is an integer which implies $2^{\frac{5(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}} \in \mathbb{Q}$. Then from (4.3), (4.4), (4.5), (4.6), we obtain that $\Phi(P) = W$, $\Phi(Q) = V$, $\Phi(R) = U$ and $\Phi(S) = T$, and hence from (4.2), $X \in \mathbb{Q}$. Therefore, $\zeta_{AVB}(-r_1, -r_2, -r_3) \in \mathbb{Q}$.

Case 2. $r_1, r_2, r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_o$ (or) $r_1, r_2 \in \mathcal{N}_e$ and $r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_o$ (or) $r_1, r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_e$ and $r_2 \in \mathcal{N}_o$ (or) $r_2, r_3 \in \mathcal{N}_e$ and $r_1 \in \mathcal{N}_o$. In this case, $(r_1 + r_2 + r_3)/2$ is not an integer, and hence $2^{\frac{5(r_1+r_2+r_3)}{2}} \in \sqrt{2}\mathbb{Q}$. Then from (4.3), (4.4), (4.5) and (4.6), we also obtain that $\Phi(P) = W$, $\Phi(Q) = V$, $\Phi(R) = U$ and $\Phi(S) = T$. Thus from (4.2), we have $X \in \mathbb{Q}$ which implies $\zeta_{AVB}(-r_1, -r_2, -r_3) \in \sqrt{2}\mathbb{Q}$. This completes the proof. \square

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